

DIRECTIONS D5.3:

Report on the stability analysis of a multiterminal offshore electrical energy hub

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Executive Summary

This report constitutes Deliverables D5.3 of Work Package 5 (WP5) within the DIRECTIONS project, which applies to *Task 5.4*. The overall DIRECTIONS control approach is illustrated in Fig. 1. This deliverable focuses on the application of the tools developed in previous work packages to relevant case studies.

Particularly, this deliverable examines the expansion of the point-to-point HVDC interconnection present in the Electrical Energy Hub (EEH) introduced in Deliverable D5.2 into a Multi-Terminal DC (MTDC) system and evaluates the resulting impact on small-signal stability. As for D5.2, the system frequency-domain characterization and small-signal stability analyses are performed using the openly available *Z-tool*.

While the system extension enhances operational capabilities, it could also introduce new dynamic interactions that must be assessed to ensure stable system performance. The analysis focuses on how converter control strategies influence the small-signal stability of the expanded system. In particular, the control of converters in grid-following (GFL) and grid-forming (GFM) modes is studied under different configurations. The study adopts a systematic approach to evaluate the dynamic behavior of an MTDC system using frequency-domain analysis tools, complemented by time-domain validation. Within this framework, the studies analyze how the different converter control modes, power flow between the offshore and onshore stations, and system configurations influence the stability of the MTDC network.

Overall, the deliverable provides a coherent framework for evaluating the small-signal stability of expanded HVDC systems, with a specific focus on understanding how stability is affected when an additional DC terminal is introduced. The study supports the ongoing development of MTDC grids by offering a structured methodology to evaluate their behavior and by clarifying the role of key design choices in ensuring reliable and stable operation.

Figure 1: DIRECTIONS control approach: this report's contents are in green.

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